

Pakistan's Hedging Dilemma amid US-China Rivalry in South Asia

Saima Mushtaq

Lecturer Government Post Graduate College for Women Mandian,
Abbottabad, email: samia.khan2846@gmail.com

Dr. Muhammad Tariq

Lecturer Department of Political Science Hazara University Mansehra,
email: muhammadtariq@hu.edu.pk

Abstract: *The US-China rivalry in the recent years, though of a different nature, is heading the world towards bipolarity with two different dynamics. The former has been engaged in the regional and global politics through the accomplishment of its geostrategic objectives while the latter engages itself as the custodian of economic development and regional connectivity through trade and business. Pakistan's position at the crossroads of South Asia, Central Asia and the Middle East gives it more significance in the global politics as a hedging state keeping in view its national interest and benefit in the international politics. The purpose of this study is to analyze Pakistan's hedging dilemma amid the US-China rivalry in South Asia. Main findings of the study include US geostrategic objectives in South Asia, China's engagement in economic development and regional connectivity and Pakistan's hedging position due to its significant location in South Asia*

Keywords: US, China, Hedging State, Rivalry, Dilemma, Strategy

Introduction

Pakistan occupies a very significant geostrategic position in the world, located at the crossroads of South Asia, Central Asia and the Middle East (Force, 2025). Its 1,046 km coastline along the Arabian Sea lying close to the Strait of Hormuz through which roughly 80% of the world's oil passes. The Gawadar Port links it to the Persian Gulf by providing the land-locked Central Asian States and Western China a direct sea route while bypassing the Strait of Malacca. (Force, 2025). This geographic location in Asia gives Pakistan a significant status for global supply chains, maritime security and competing great power strategies. The nuclear capability of the state further adds to the influence over the security dynamics in the regional politics (Force, 2025). Its role as a peace mediator in the recent US-Iran conflict for facilitating peace parleys between the US and Iran further gives strength to its position in its efforts to resolve major

disputes through arbitration (Tariq & Mushtaq, 2026). Besides, it acts as a key player in the global war on terror and acts as a gateway for China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Both the United States and China, who are busy in competing for influence in Eurasia, view Pakistan through the prism of their geopolitical objectives. Due to the geographic importance of Pakistan, both Washington and Beijing regard Pakistan's strategic importance through high-level contacts, initiatives and narrative building leading to convergence and divergence in their approaches towards Pakistan (Force, 2025).

Pak-China Friendship and Strategic Partnership

Both Pakistan and China enjoys cordial relations for decades and often share the same opinion on all major issues and disputes in the global politics. For China, Pakistan is an important and indispensable partner in its Belt and Road Initiative since the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor connects China's western region to the Arabian Sea that plays a key role in the trade and business activities of the of countries (Force, 2025). The Gawadar Port provides direct access to the Arabian Sea while bypassing the Strait of Malacca and serving as a gateway to Central Asian Countries and the Middle East. The port's proximity to the Strait of Hormuz further increases its strategic value for energy security and maritime trade. The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) includes highways, rail lines, energy pipelines and industrial zones connecting Gawadar to Kashgar in Xinjiang. The Chinese Prime Minister's, Li Qiang's visit to Pakistan in October 2024, whereby a 'joint statement' reaffirmed their bilateral relations as "rock-solid" and committed to upgrading CPEC by building "growth, livelihood, innovation, green and open corridors" improving the Main Line-1 railway (ML-1) and enhancing the Gawadar Port (Force, 2025). While Pakistan reiterated its support for China's One-China Principle and Beijing's reciprocation for safeguarding Pakistan's sovereignty and national security (Force, 2025).

Since 1960s, both the countries described their relationship as an "all-weather" relationship built on common stance over key areas. In June 2024, Chinese President, Xi Jinping called Pakistan a "good-neighbor, good-friend, good-partner and good-brother". He further added that China would continue to support Pakistan's sovereignty and territorial integrity and help in combating terrorism. Security cooperation between the two states is a cornerstone of their mutual understanding, whereas China provides Pakistan military hardware, from combat aircraft and naval frigates to surface-to-surface missiles (Force, 2025). During July 2025, in a joint meeting between China's top diplomat Wang Yi and Pakistan's Chief of

Defense Forces, Gen. Asim Munir, wherein the Chinese diplomat called Pakistani military a “staunch defender of national interests” (Force, 2025). Gen. Asim Munir responded that cooperation with China enjoyed consensus in Pakistani society and pledged to safeguard Chinese nationals and strengthen counter-terrorism cooperation (Force, 2025).

China’s reemergence as a great power, and the ensuing competition with the United States over the norms, rules, and values signifying the international order, signals the return of great power rivalry in global politics (Boni, 2026). At the very heart of these dynamics, lie the Belt and Road Initiative and the Free and Open Indo-Pacific strategies, with implications for the Asian States with an exploration of navigating the US-China Rivalry (Boni, 2026). The US-China rivalry encompasses political, economic and technological domains coupled with their interest in several world regions. Nowhere in the world is the new great power competition between China and the United States more intense and evident than in Asia where there has always been the clash of interest between the two major powers (Boni, 2026). The two powers have been engaged in foreign policy initiatives, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and the Free and Open Indo-Pacific (FOIP) deployed by China and America in the past decades.

The Free and Open Indo-Pacific Strategy

The Free and Open Indo-Pacific (FOIP) strategy focuses on increasing economic security and supply chain resilience within the Indo-Pacific aiming at developing cooperation with the ASEAN countries (Kamisuna, 2026). Japan is also concerned with the strengthening of security in the region as is evident from his visit to Hanoi in Vietnam on May 2, 2026 whereby Japan’s Prime Minister, Takaichi Senae, urged on Japan’s Free and Open Indo-Pacific for its policy towards the region (Kamisuna, 2026). The FOIP aims at a strong emphasis on practical outcomes for Southeast Asia and the broader Indo-Pacific region in three areas; building economic infrastructure, boosting economic growth and enhancing security against ‘the structural change in the international order’ (Kamisuna, 2026). Japan showed its concern with the FOIP during 2016 at China’s growing influence in the Indo-Pacific and pledged to preserve maritime security and the rule of law in the region. Japan also designs the FOIP to be inclusive of many countries in the region, particularly in ASEAN, and no one to be forced to choose between aligning with China or the United States (Kamisuna, 2026).

The FOIP has three basic pillars; the first pillar deals with supporting economic resilience in the region by including the infrastructure of both the economic and strategic paradigms (Kamisuna, 2026). Tokyo plans to focus on supporting capacity building in areas such as

artificial intelligence and flow of technology, as well as in key areas for digital connectivity such as under seas cables and satellite communications in strengthening the FOIP Digital Corridor Concept (Kamisuna, 2026). The second pillar deals with the development of public-private schemes for promoting cooperation and rule-sharing within the Indo-Pacific for supporting regional economic growth (Kamisuna, 2026). Tokyo has been seeking leverage in strategic sectors such as energy, infrastructure and finance in Southeast Asia. The Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific (CPTPP); a free trade agreement with Japan's largest economy and would contain six ASEAN countries if Indonesia and Philippines join the agreement (Kamisuna, 2026). The third pillar deals with the expansion of Japan's Official Security Assistance (OSA) and Official Development Assistance (ODA). To support this, the Takaichi cabinet has allocated 18.1 billion yen (US \$116 million) for OSA for FY 2026 more than double the 8.1 billion yen (US \$54.12m) earmarked for FY 2025 (Kamisuna, 2026). The OSA would likely remain focused on Southeast Asian Countries on account of the strategic importance of the region. The FOIP will also enhance the use of ODA for security, including port and airport development for Pacific Island countries as initial projects (Kamisuna, 2026). Japan's ODA budget also increased in FY 2026 for the first time in three years, reaching around 580 billion yen (US \$3.75bn) and also intends the OSA and the ODA to work together for deepening its defense across the indo-Pacific.

Implications of the US-China Rivalry

The US-China competition has been reshaping the global order, posing challenges for states in the Asia-Pacific region (Jamal & Hussain, 2026). This rivalry between the two major powers besides, posing challenges to the regional dynamics, also poses strategic challenges for Pakistan on account of its geostrategic position and location in the region (Jamal & Hussain, 2026). The challenges compel Pakistan to reconsider its historical alliances, redefine economic and security priorities, and resultantly reshape its viable policy responses in placing itself in the global landscape. But the challenges are always tied with opportunities as is evident from the recent US-Iran conflict and Pakistan's mediating role in resolving the conflict. US President, Donald Trump has been appreciative of the efforts taken by the Pakistani Prime Minister, Shahbaz Sharif and Chief of Defense Forces, Gen. Asim Munir in facilitating the peace talks between the belligerent states. Pakistan's role revolves around the pragmatic hedging in its geostrategic engagement with the United States and its geo-economic and geo-strategic partnership with China based on the doctrine of 'no-enemy stance' through balancing competition and maximization of benefits from both (Jamal & Hussain, 2026).

The ongoing US-China rivalry has become a paradigm of international relations shaping the trajectory of international order (Li, 2025). It encompasses political, security and economic domains. The economic competition and trade and finance related conflicts constitute a tangible aspect of the rivalry, with the technological parameter of the rivalry running deeper coupled with security implications for the regional dynamics (Li, 2025). The main reason behind the current state of affairs and the international order was shaped by the US in the post-world war- II with four key pillars: a capitalist world economy through the Bretton Woods System, dominance of dollar in the international markets, and the global economic interdependence, collective security under the umbrella of the US-led alliances in Europe and Asia for countering communism, a global trade regime centered on Europe and East Asia, and the liberal ideological alignment promoting American norms and values (Li, 2025).

China is considered as a ‘systemic rival’ to the US-led international order. The concept of systemic rival opines a strong perception of the China’s global rise in not only turning the country into a global economic and technological competitor but also converting its economic success into a political and ideological force aiming at the development of the alternative models of development and governance (Li, 2025). Keeping in view the global challenges, benefits of globalization, shared values, advancement of technological developments and the digitalization of the world system, it is imperative that the two rival powers may live in peaceful co-existence while contributing to human progress and prosperity. Peaceful co-existence and contributing towards humanity may help the belligerent nations work in close collaboration and increase interdependence in the wake of globalization, improvement in communication and transportations, increased role of social media, the use of artificial intelligence, horrors of war, use of nuclear technology, cyber warfare and digitalization of the entire world.

The US-China rivalry can also be seen through the prism of structure-agency interactions going beyond the conventional frameworks of international relations and international political economy (Li, 2025). In the post-World War-II scenario, the US hegemonic agency has been playing an active role in maintaining international order and fostering international cooperation. The growth of globalization has brought about drastic changes in the *modus operandi* of the capitalist economy wherein the economic orders constitute rules and regulative capabilities responsible for restructuring and generating new social patterns of actors and agencies (Li, 2025). The conventional structural power of the US agency in the international political economy, (security, production, finance, and knowledge production) has largely been diluted. While during the past four decades, Beijing has gained a

new level of agential power making it a geopolitical competitor in the existing international system (Li, 2025).

The rivalry between the US and China within the South Asian security environment is very important where the US has been investing in India by counter-balancing China, while Pakistan has developed ties with China (Boni, 2026). The US-China rivalry may influence Pakistan's relations with the US and may greatly impact the regional stability and the international order since Pakistan would more likely move towards China for maintaining friendly relations. Historically speaking, Pakistan has maintained strong relations with both the US and China keeping in view the political, economic and security paradigms. Pakistan's relationships with US include its support for the war against terrorism in the post-9/11, 2021 scenario and its role in the recent US-Iran conflict as a peace mediator beside cooperation in other areas (Boni, 2026). China has become the largest supplier of arms to Pakistan, besides initiating unprecedented cooperation through CPEC having a projected value of \$62 billion (Boni, 2026). China has also supported Pakistan against India on the issue of Kashmir and has also helped Pakistan internationalize the issue of Kashmir.

US-China Rivalry and its impact on Pakistan

The US-China rivalry not only creates opportunities and complications within Pakistan itself but also influences Pakistan's relations with other key regional powers (Ali, 2020). The US-India growing synergy in the Indo-Pacific for curbing the influence of China has is also worth-mentioning (Ali, 2020). The US-China rivalry could also exacerbate the prolonged India-Pakistan conflict by increasing advanced arms and intelligence capabilities on both sides (Ali, 2020). The US strategists pointed out opportunities for Washington to accelerate and deepen its collaboration with New Delhi in the India's ongoing border dispute with China. India's deepening of dependence on Russia also arises out of the rivalry between the major powers in the Indo-Pacific (Ali, 2020).

The US-China rivalry also impacts Pakistan's relations in the Middle East. Pakistan has to face some recent friction with traditional US ally Saudi Arabia on account of its reluctance for supporting the stance of Pakistan over the issue of Kashmir. China again took the initiative and provided another \$1 billion loan for repaying to Saudi Arabia. Both the Gulf States and Saudi Arabia develop close economic ties and show interest to make investments in each other countries. Any drastic shift by Pakistan away from the US-aligned Gulf States like the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Saudi Arabia, and Bahrain to a China-backed alignment comprising

Iran, Turkey, and Malaysia would be an overreach and may not be in line with Pakistan's strategic interest (Ali, 2020). Most of the Muslim States may diverge in their relations with China particularly on regional and global issues and would rather have more inclination towards the United States but for Pakistan, both the United States and China are important on account of the strategic economic and security interest. Pakistan had to make decision via alliances while keeping in view its strategic interest and benefit in the regional politics and national interest. But objectives and priorities in national interest differ from time to time and state to state depending on nature and geographical interest. For security parameters, Pakistan had to uphold the cause of the United States but when it comes to economic development and investment, Pakistan has to stand by China. In the current changing dynamics of the global politics and security requirements, China is the only country and time tested friend of Pakistan that can serve the economic as well as security interests of Pakistan.

The US-China rivalry can also be seen through the lens of global trade war, as is evident from the recent visit of the US President, Donald Trump and Chinese President, Xi Jinping to South Korea (Mehdi, 2025). During the meeting both the states agreed to have bilateral trade and business in key areas. China agreed to suspend export controls on rare earth minerals and purchasing of agricultural products including soybeans, from the United States. While the United States, in return reduced the fentanyl tariff from 20% to 10% and pausing the expansion of the export control list that had previously panelized Chinese companies (Mehdi, 2025). The Seoul meeting signifies a shift in US-China competition from tariff diplomacy to resource security. The US-China competition would increasingly determine and resultantly shape the global power dynamics as both the major powers aim at controlling key technologies, supply chains and trade flows (Mehdi, 2025). In the face of further intensification of the rivalry, Pakistan may face challenges requiring it to balance between the two great powers.

Since both Pakistan and China are celebrating 75 years of their diplomatic relations, it is in the interest of the two states to cope with the rapidly changing world and international order (Amir, 2026). China has now been considered as one of the superpowers alongside the United States (Amir, 2026). The rising power of China as an economic giant and superpower while sharing common border with Pakistan, it may have implications, opportunities, dependencies, pressures and strategic dilemmas for Pakistan in its dealings with other major powers in the world (Amir, 2026). But it is also important that Pakistan's association with the US has been through fluctuating phases of cooperation, mistrust, and transactional alignments (Amir, 2026). Although both the super powers share the goal of terrorism-free neighborhood

and their views broadly converge on Afghanistan yet there is divergence over the way of addressing the problem. The changing security dynamics of the world has compelled Pakistan to reshape its Afghan policy while China has maintained a consistent and pragmatic approach based on engagement, mediation and gradual stabilization (Amir, 2026).

New Dynamics of Pak-US Ties

In the wake of May 2025 Pak-India skirmishes, Pakistan emerged as a renewed ally of the US, gaining military aid and economic investments, yet relations remain transitional due to the US engagement in some regional and global issues (Zaman, 2026). China's relations with Pakistan are mainly economic based focusing on China Pakistan Economic Corridor but also help Pakistan in logistic and moral support on all important issues. In the May 2025 skirmishes between Pakistan and India, China has also to provide Pakistan with assistance and support. But after all, in pursuance of navigating US-China rivalry, Pakistan needs to pursue a balanced and multilateral diplomacy for safeguarding its national interest and core objectives of maintaining friendly relations. During the May 2025 Pak-India episode, relations between Pakistan and the US were in high spirits, whereby the latter helped Pakistan in the ceasefire and brining peace between the two arch-rivals while the Pakistani authorities have to nominate the US President, Donald Trump for Noble Prize (Amir, 2026).

Economy and Technology

Economy and technology form the central part of the US-China competition as was highlighted in the events of 2025 setting the foundational importance of these key areas (Medeiros, 2026). This is not an example of relative advantage but shows a competitive environment for leverage with both sides seeking to identify and exploit vulnerabilities while maximizing their own benefits (Medeiros, 2026). The events of 2025 show more resemblance to a supply chain rather than traditional trade war. The two states have now transitioned to a new phase of competition with matters of technological strength and vulnerabilities being at the forefront (Medeiros, 2026). China seems to avail this phase through better preparation, with developed and new economic weapons, while re-engineering its domestic economy for resilience. Conversely, the US has to combat the monumental challenge of coordinating industrial policy across government and private industry (Medeiros, 2026). It is also important that the degree of the spillover of the US-China competition would be greater than that of US-Soviet rivalry due to the baseline level of bilateral and global interdependence.

Many analysts are of the view that China is now acknowledging itself as an emerging global power (Rana, 2026). It is important to mention that for nearly a decade, China tried to avoid projecting itself as a challenger to the international order, and opted to cultivate the image of the leader of the global South besides showing willingness for becoming a partner of the developing economies power (Rana, 2026). In the wake of the changing dynamics at the global level leading towards bipolarity between China and the US, Pakistan would be positioned at the intersection of great power competition coupled with two diverse dynamics, the economic dependence and the regional strategic realignment. Though Pakistan's strategic alliance with the US has been helpful in shaping Pakistan's foreign policy and strategic objectives yet the recent emergence of China in the global politics may be of more importance for Pakistan on account of both the economic dependence as well as the security dynamics.

Discussion and Conclusion

The recent US-China competition is leading the world towards bipolarity with both the US and China as two poles apart. Each competitor is busy in gaining as much friends as possible particularly countries like Pakistan that enjoys a very strategic position in the regional politics. In the recent US-China rivalry, Pakistan has been playing the role of a hedging state depending on the nature of the interest and based on its cost and benefit analysis. It is the geostrategic position of Pakistan that attracts the major powers towards it. Located at the crossroads of South Asia, Central Asia and the Middle East and its 1,046 km coastline along the Arabian Sea brings it closer to the Strait of Hormuz. The Gawadar Port is an additional point for Pakistan making it link to the Persian Gulf by providing the land-locked Central Asian States and the Western China with a direct sea route in lieu of bypassing the Strait of Malacca. Pakistan's nuclear capability is another area of great concern making it more important for the regional and global dynamics coupled with its victory in May 2025 Pak-India skirmishes and active role as a peace mediator in the recent US-Iran conflict. Its active engagement in the war on terror against terrorism and acting as a gateway to China's Belt and Road Initiative gives additional strength to Pakistan where it is being viewed through the prism of geopolitical objectives.

Pakistan's engagement in the world affairs and its role in resolving the regional disputes, make both the US and China to consider Pakistan on account of its high level contact, initiatives and narrative building leading to convergence and divergence. National interest and objectives of a state in regional dynamics determines the prospects of convergence or divergence depending on the relative gains and maximization of benefits. But Pakistan has also

to keep in mind its geostrategic objectives for which it has been making alliance with the US for decades but when it comes to the economic interest and gains, China has always been there to reach out to Pakistan. The changing security and economic dynamics at both the regional and the global level has made Pakistan closer to China yet at the same time the importance of the US cannot be gainsaid as during the May 2025 skirmishes between Pakistan and India and Pakistan's recent role as a peace mediator in the US-Iran conflict proved its true worth when Pakistan has to receive high applause from all the global quarters.

Pakistan's economic development and the resultant initiatives in the form of China Pakistan Economic Corridor including the highways, rail lines, energy pipelines, and industrial zones connecting Gawadar to Kashgar is of great significance for the trading and business communities across the regional powers. Moreover, the Belt and Road Initiative and the Free and Open Indo-Pacific strategies has great significance for the Asian States and its further impact on the US-China rivalry leading to multi-faceted aspects of politics, economy and the technology. The FIOP aims at increasing economic security and supply chains resilience within the Indo-Pacific with the objective of developing cooperation with the ASEAN Countries. The Indo-Pacific focuses on three areas: building the economic infrastructure, boosting economic growth and enhancing security against the structural change in the international order. Besides, the FOIP has three key pillars: the first one dealing with supporting economic resilience in the region, the second one dealing with the development of public-private schemes for the promotion of cooperation and rule-sharing within the Indo-Pacific and the third one talking about the expansion of Japan's Official Security Assistance and Official Development Assistance.

The main focus of the United States in the post-World War-II scenario emphasized four key pillars: the establishment of a capitalist world economic order through the Bretton Woods System, the excessive dominance of the dollar in the international market as a standard unit for most of the countries, the need for the global economic interdependence and the concept of collective security under the umbrella of the US-led alliances in Europe and Asia for countering communism. On the other hand, China mainly focuses on the economic capacity building of the world market mechanism through transportation of goods, need for the increased supply and demand of goods and construction of more projects like CPEC for the regional connectivity, improvement in software technology and digitalization of the world. In such a scenario, China is considered as the 'system rival' aiming at the conversion of the state into a

global economic and technological competitor and converting that success into political and ideological force.

References

Ali , S. M. (2020, December 1). The U.S.-China Strategic Rivalry and its Implications for Pakistan. *Stimson* . <https://www.stimson.org/2020/the-u-s-china-strategic-rivalry-and-its-implications-for-pakistan/>.

Boni, F. (2026, May 29). The US-China Rivalry in South Asia and Pakistan’s hedging dilemma. *Asia Maior*(Asia Maior Special Issue 2 / 2022).

Force, A. T. (2025, July 28). Pakistan’s Strategic Importance in the Eyes of the US and China: Interactions, Initiatives and High Level Contacts. *Beyond the Horizon*. <https://behorizon.org/pakistans-strategic-importance-in-the-eyes-of-the-us-and-china-interactions-initiatives-and-high-level-contacts/>.

Jamal, A. , & Hussain, M. ,. (2206, May 5). Examining Pakistan's Strategic Hedging Between the United States and China. *Pacific Focus, Inha Journal of Intenrational Studeis, Wiley Online*.

Kamisuna, T. (2026, May 22). Japan’s update of its Free and Open Indo-Pacific framework. *Facts, Analysis and Influence*. <https://www.iiss.org/online-analysis/online-analysis/2026/05/japan-update-of-its-free-and-open-indo-pacific-framework/>.

Li, X. (2025, July 25). Conceptualizing China–U.S. rivalry through the lens of globalization in an era of changing structure-agency dynamics. *Taylor and Francis Online* , 23(3. 2026), 389-407.

Medeiros, E. S. (2026, April 21). A New Era of US-China Interaction. *Hinrich Foundation*. https://www.hinrichfoundation.com/research/wp/trade-geopolitics/a-new-era-of-us-china-interaction?utm_source=google&utm_medium=ppc&utm_campaign=wp-medeiros-a-new-era-us-china-relations&utm_content=20260519-static&utm_term=&utm_campaign=&utm_source=adwords.

Mehdi, M. K. (2025, November 28). Pakistan at the Crossroads of the US–China Strategic Minerals Rivalry. <https://ciss.org.pk/pakistan-at-the-crossroads-of-the-us-china-strategic-minerals-rivalry/>.

Rana , M. A. (2026, May 24). Neighbor to a Super Power. *Dawn, International Newspaper* .
<https://www.dawn.com/news/2002685>.

Rana , M. A. (2026, May 17). Pak-China-US triangle. *Sawn, International Newspaper*.
<https://www.dawn.com/news/2000842>.

Tariq, M., & Mushtaq, S. (2026, March 26). The Strait of Hormuz: A Gateway to World's Trade and Business. *Journal of Media Horizon*, 7(3), 707-714.

Tariq, M., Shah , S. J., & Rasheed, L. (2026, 3 15). The Geopolitical Significance of the Strait of Hormuz in the Global Politics: An Appraisal. *Research Consortium Archive*, 4(1), 1405-1516.

Zaman, Z. (2026, February 24). Pakistan's Tightrope: Between America's Embrace and China's Shadow. *News, Fair Observer* . <https://www.fairobserver.com/politics/pakistans-tightrope-between-americas-embrace-and-chinas-shadow/>.